

AGU 2022 FALL

NAME: NASA TOPS

WEEK: DECEMBER 11-16

SESSION

TASKS	S	M	T	W	T	F	
SMD STRATEGIC CONTENT 8:30-3:30, MARRIOTT MARQUIS CHICAGO, ROOM GREAT LAKES A, LEVEL 2; 2121 S PRAIRIE AVE	✓						
<u>OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES AND SUCCESS STORIES</u> (2:45-4:15, 4:45-6:15) - MCCORMICK PLACE - N426C		✓					ED15B/ ED16B
EXHIBIT 3-6PM		✓					
<u>DATA AND OPEN SCIENCE FOR COMMUNITIES</u> (6:30-7:30) - McCormick Place - S104a		✓					TH15G
<u>ENABLING THE USE OF EARTH OBSERVATIONS FOR EQUITY AND ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE</u> (12:45-1:45) - MCCORMICK PLACE - S106A			✓				TH23E
<u>NASA OPEN SCIENCE EVENTS, CURRICULA, AND OPPORTUNITIES</u> (12:45-1:45) - MCCORMICK PLACE - S103CD				✓			TH33H
TRANSFORM TO OPEN SCIENCE HYPERWALL TALK (4:40-4:50)				✓			
<u>NASA SMD OPEN-SOURCE SCIENCE INITIATIVE</u> (6:30-7:30 PM) - MCCORMICK PLACE - S103CD				✓			TH35H
EXHIBIT 10AM-6PM			✓	✓			
SCIENCE DISCOVERY ENGINE HYPERWALL TALK 10-11 AM					✓		
EXHIBIT 10AM-1PM					✓		
<u>THE FUTURE IS OPEN INNOVATION</u> (9-10:30) - MCCORMICK PLACE - GRAND BALLROOM S100						✓	INV52B
<u>GREAT DEBATE</u> (2:45-3:15) - MCCORMICK PLACE - N427A-D						✓	U55A